

Further Studies on Anthraquinone Derivatives from *Tectona grandis**

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Jaipur-302 004Manuscript received 29 January 1991,
accepted 7 November 1991

TECTONA grandis Linn. f. (Verbenaceae) popularly known as 'teak' or 'sagwan', occurs in all tropical and subtropical regions. Earlier work on this plant led to the isolation of a number of compounds¹. We reinvestigated a Sawai Madhopur collection of teakwood and reported a new 1,4-anthraquinone derivative² and three 9,10-anthraquinone derivatives (1-3) as minor constituents along with the previously reported compounds. The present report deals with the isolation and characterisation of these rare and minor 9,10-anthraquinone derivatives (1-3).

Experimental

The air-dried powdered heartwood shavings of *T. grandis* (5 kg) was extracted with petrol (b.p. 60-80°) on a steam-bath (3 × 12 h) and the extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure. The reddish brown semi-solid mass was taken up in ether and fractionated into acidic and neutral parts by extracting with 2*N* Na₂CO₃ solution. The Na₂CO₃-soluble part on neutralisation with 6*N* HCl furnished lapachol (20 mg) as bright yellow crystals, m.p. 139-40°. The Na₂CO₃-insoluble part (neutral fraction) was column chromatographed over deactivated neutral alumina and afforded tectoquinone as brown needles (500 mg), m.p. 174-76° from the petrol, tecomaquinone-I as green blue needles (50 mg), m.p. 198-99° from the petrol-benzene (1 : 1), dehydro- α -lapachone as red needles (45 mg), m.p. 143-44° from benzene, and 9,10-dimethoxy-2-methyl-1,4-anthraquinone as yellow crystals (12 mg) from the C₆H₆-EtOAc (9 : 1) eluates. The C₆H₆-EtOAc (3 : 1) fraction afforded a mixture of three anthraquinone derivatives (70 mg) which on repeated prep-tlc gave **1** (20 mg) and **3** (15 mg). The molecular formulae of the quinones (**1-3**) could be established as C₁₆H₁₀O₄ (238.0632),

C₁₆H₁₂O₄ (268.0734) and C₁₆H₁₀O₄ (254.0577). The presence of hydrogen bonded OH groups, unchelated and chelated C=O groups was ascertained by the appearance of broad bands at 3 350 and sharp bands at 1 670 and 1 640-1 630 cm⁻¹ respectively. The presence of chelated hydroxyls was also confirmed by the appearance of sharp singlets in down-field region (δ 12.12-13.30 ppm) in the ¹H nmr spectra. The sequence of the protons was established by spin-decoupling experiments.

5-Hydroxy-2-methyl-9,10-anthraquinone (1): It gave yellow crystals (20 mg), m.p. 146-47° (lit.³ 147°); $\nu_{\max}$ (CCl₄) 3 350 (OH), 1 670 (unchelated C=O), 1 640 (chelated C=O), 1 580 and 1 560 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ (400 MHz; CDCl₃) 8.12 (br s, H-1), 8.21 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-4), 7.85 (dd, *J* 8, 1.5 Hz, H-8), 7.63 (dd, *J* 8, 1.5 Hz, H-6), 7.32 (dd, *J* 8, 1.5 Hz, H-3), 7.69 (t, *J* 8 Hz, H-7), 12.64 (s, OH) and 2.55 (s, CH₃); *m/z* (rel. int.) 238.0632 [*M*⁺] (C₁₆H₁₀O₄), (100), 223 [*M*-Me]⁺ (6), 210 [*M*-Co]⁺ (8), 195 [223-CO]⁺ (4), 182 [210-CO]⁺ (12) and 181 [210-CHO]⁺ (14).

1-Hydroxy-5-methoxy-2-methyl-9,10-anthraquinone (2): It gave yellow crystals (20 mg), m.p. 183-84° (lit.⁴ 189-91°); $\nu_{\max}$ (CCl₄) 3 350 (OH), 1 670, 1 630 (C=O), 1 590 and 1 560 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ (400 MHz; CDCl₃) 7.98 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-8), 7.71 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-4), 7.76 (t, *J* 8 Hz, H-7), 7.51 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-3), 7.38 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-6), 4.09 (s, OCH₃), 2.38 (s, CH₃), 13.30 (s, OH); *m/z* (rel. int.) 268.0734 [*M*⁺] (C₁₆H₁₂O₄) (100), 253 [*M*-Me]⁺ (8), 240 [*M*-Co]⁺ (4), 239 [*M*-CHO]⁺ (18), 237 [*M*-OMe]⁺ (4), 222 [237-Me]⁺ (26) and 149 (38).

1,5-Dihydroxy-2-methyl-9,10-anthraquinone (3): It gave yellow crystals (15 mg), m.p. 195-96° (lit.⁴ 196-97°); $\nu_{\max}$ (CCl₄) 3 350 (OH), 1 625 (chelated C=O), 1 610, 1 580 and 1 560 cm⁻¹; δ (400 MHz; CDCl₃) 7.86 (dd, *J* 8, 1 Hz, H-8), 7.79 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-4), 7.70 (t, *J* 8 Hz, H-7), 7.58 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-3), 7.30 (dd, *J* 8, 1 Hz, H-6), 2.39 (s, CH₃), 12.12 (s, OH), 12.42 (s, OH); *m/z* (rel. int.) 254.0577 [*M*⁺] (C₁₆H₁₀O₄) (100), 239 [*M*-Me]⁺ (20), 237 [*M*-OH]⁺ (18), 226 [*M*-Co]⁺ (4), 209 [237-Co]⁺ (4) and 149 (70).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance and Professor R. H. Thomson for expert opinion.

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* Presented at the International Symposium on the Biology and Chemistry of Active Natural Substances, 1990 held at Bonn, West Germany.

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